

Resilient Automatic Model Selection for Mobility Prediction

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Abstract

In order to avoid extensive machine learning models selection and optimizations, Automated Machine Learning (AutoML) has arisen as a practical and efficient way to apply machine learning to many different application areas. Data poisoning is a real threat to the accuracy of machine learning models in different settings, and it has in recent research studies been shown that the usage of AutoML can be even more sensitive to data poisoning than is the case for non-AutoML generated models. On the other hand, the usage of AutoML also has the potential of *improving* the robustness of a model by adapting the model to adversarial patterns. In this way, good accuracy can be maintained *despite* the attacker's efforts to poison the data. However, no previous studies have investigated these effects. In this paper, we examine the risks associated with adversarial trajectory attacks in mobile systems, specifically looking into mobility prediction problems. By using mobility data from two different simulation frameworks: a simulator developed by Ericsson, which is based on a real-world deployment of Airtel's open-network topology, and the ONE framework, we investigate three different AutoML frameworks and how the mobility accuracy for the frameworks is affected by a mobile trajectory attack. Our results show that re-running AutoML at every retraining is vulnerable to adversarial mobility poisoning and shows high accuracy variance. By contrast, using a single, well-chosen model from an initial AutoML search achieves more stable performance across adversarial conditions, even when the training set includes up to 10% adversarial mobility data.

1 Introduction

Data poisoning can be a severe threat to machine learning models [1]. Lots of previous research studies have investigated the effects of data poisoning under various conditions and with different threat assumptions. In a recent research study, Pang et. al [2] showed that Automated Machine Learning (AutoML) can have a negative impact, making the system even more sensitive to data poisoning compared to using a predefined model. AutoML, on the other hand, has arisen as a powerful and swift approach to apply machine learning to real-life problems [3]. The main benefit comes from the fact that model selection and hyperparameter selection can be a manual and cumbersome task to undertake, which prevents the adoption of the technologies. This has given rise to lots of new research contributions in the field [4].

One natural application area for AutoML is mobility trajectory prediction, forecasting future user equipment (UE) locations in mobile networks. For example, mobility predictions have enabled substantial reductions in paging signaling—over 90% improvement has been reported using data from a Korean 5G operator [5, 6]. In this respect, the 5G network standard includes the Network Data Analytics Function (NWDAF) 3GPP [7, 8]. NWDAF leverages machine learning (ML) to optimize network performance, reduce operational costs, and enhance user experience. This embraces mobility prediction as an NWDAF analytics service. Regular retraining of NWDAF models is mandated by standards to ensure predictive accuracy, but this process can be resource-intensive and complex when conducted manually. AutoML simplifies the model selection task for operators. However, despite this fact, few works address how AutoML affects prediction accuracy under data poisoning conditions. While AutoML clearly can increase the risk, under some attack model assumptions, it certainly also might have the possibility to instead *increase the robustness* in the system against position attacks. This is the research hypothesis investigated in this paper. We explore the hypothesis in a threat model where the attacker *only* can influence the training data by introducing adversarial mobility patterns into the network. This is a reasonable assumption, as any potential attacker can acquire legitimate mobile equipment and try to introduce strange mobility patterns that can affect the mobility prediction accuracy.

AutoML is a large research field with many different approaches for both suitable architecture selection and hyperparameter optimizations. While it is not feasible to investigate all different frameworks concerning the sensitivity to attacks in a mobility prediction scenario, we can select a representative subset of the frameworks and compare their attack robustness. This is the approach we have taken in this paper, investigating and comparing the performance of Auto-sklearn [9], AutoGluon [10], and FLAML [11] frameworks. To test our research hypothesis for these frameworks, we

examine two primary retraining strategies to mitigate the impact of adversarial mobility attacks: (A) employing AutoML to reselect the model at each retraining iteration, and (B) retraining the initial model discovered by AutoML.

The main contributions of this paper are the following:

- We provide complete mobility datasets with and without adversarial mobility patterns in the network using two different simulated data sets. The first data set is obtained based on a real-world deployment of Airtel’s open-network topology in India, and a second data set is obtained from the fully open ONE simulator framework [12].
- We investigate the impact of adversarial mobility movements on the model selection and retraining with three different AutoML frameworks for mobility prediction.
- We analyze the outcome of the experiments and find an AutoML usage and training strategy that gives good prediction accuracy for legitimate UEs despite the presence of adversarial mobile movements in the network

The present work is a rework of a previous conference paper [13]. In this paper, we expand the scope of the previous research study, taking a broader set of related work into account and considerably extending the experimental evaluation. We present experimental results not only using one mobile network simulator but two different. In particular, the added ONE framework has allowed us to release all the simulation source code and corresponding data.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows. Section 2 surveys related work. Section 3 provides an overview of the NWDAF model lifecycle and the problem statement. Section 4 describes the operator retraining strategies considered in this study. Section 5 presents the threat model. Section 6 details the modeling of UE mobility. Section 7 discusses the simulation setup and results. Section 8 reviews threats to the validity of the results. Finally, Section 9 concludes the paper and outlines future research directions.

2 Related Work

In this section, we review the related literature from the following three different research areas: The first area is automated machine learning, which has received considerable attention in recent years. The second area is mobility prediction. Finally, we give an overview of related work on adversarial machine learning.

2.1 Automated Machine Learning (AutoML)

AutoML automates the selection of suitable models for specific datasets and tasks, typically involving data preparation, feature engineering, model generation, and evaluation [4, 14]. It aims to reduce development costs and simplify model deployment [15]. Model generation, especially hyperparameter optimization and neural architecture search, has garnered the most research interest. Notably, Zoph and Le introduced neural architecture search via reinforcement learning [16].

Thornton et al. [17] defined the Combined Algorithm Selection and Hyperparameter optimization (CASH) problem, demonstrating its efficiency through Bayesian

optimization in Auto-WEKA. Subsequent works have produced various frameworks, with some, like Optuna [18], focusing exclusively on hyperparameter optimization, and others addressing specialized learning tasks. This is, for instance, the case for the TODS tool [19], which offers automatic model selection for outlier detection, where Nguyen et al. [20] highlighted Bayesian optimization’s effectiveness.

Table 1 Relevant AutoML frameworks.

Reference	Principle	Evaluated in the paper
Auto-WEKA [17]	Bayesian Optimization	No
Optuna [18]	Software framework for parameter optimization	No
TODS [19]	Graphical tool for Directed Acyclic Graph pipelines	No
Auto-sklearn [9]	Bayesian Optimization	Yes
Autogluon [10]	Stacked Ensembles of Pre-set Pipelines	Yes
FLAML [11]	Cost Frugal Optimization	Yes

Early CASH studies did not optimize hyperparameter tuning costs in terms of time and complexity. Wu et al. [21] addressed this by introducing a cost-efficient optimization method.

Alternatively, the CASH complexity can be avoided by using model stacking, which automatically selects optimal models via layer-wise training with arbitrary machine learning models. Despite limiting the model search space, this approach has proven highly effective in practice, as demonstrated by AutoGluon [10].

Studying the impact of adversarial data poisoning requires selecting state-of-the-art representative AutoML frameworks that illustrate diverse optimization approaches. Using this selection criteria, we choose three different frameworks to be included into the evaluation: Auto-sklearn [9], AutoGluon [10], and FLAML [11]. Table 1 gives an overview of different frameworks and the optimization principles used in the frameworks. Each framework selected for the study utilizes distinct strategies: Auto-sklearn leverages Bayesian optimization [22], while AutoGluon integrates a combination of techniques, including ensembling, stacking [23], multi-fidelity optimization [24], and bandit-based resource allocation [25], to enhance model performance and ensure efficient model selection. Additionally, AutoGluon employs Neural Architecture Search (NAS) [26] to optimize models, striking a balance between performance and search efficiency. On the other hand, FLAML is a lightweight AutoML tool that adopts an adaptive ensemble learning approach, enabling the construction of high-performing models with minimal computational overhead.

2.2 Mobility prediction

A defining characteristic of mobile networks is their ability to manage mobile units and maintain communication quality while users are on the move. With the advent of 5G and its reliance on smaller cells, this challenge has intensified, as cell updates occur far more frequently compared to previous generations of mobile networks [27].

One promising solution to ensure seamless connectivity is the ability to predict the next cell or user trajectory with high precision [28]. Accurate and robust mobility prediction, in turn, enables the optimization of radio and network resources while reducing handover latency.

Table 2 Machine learning mobility predictions approaches by year.

Reference	ML Approach	Year
[29]	Markov Chain	2010
[30]	Markov Chain	2012
[31]	Feedforward Neural Network	2014
[32]	Hidden Markov Chain	2014
[33]	Random Forest	2018
[34]	LSTM	2019
[35]	Hidden Markov Chain	2018
[36]	Hidden Markov Chain	2021
[37]	STD-Net	2021
[38]	DHSTNet	2021
[39]	LSTM	2022
[40]	LSTM	2022
[41]	Lightweight Artificial Neural Network	2023

State-of-the-art mobility prediction methods encompass a range of techniques, including traditional Machine Learning [29–33, 35, 36, 42, 43] and advanced Deep Learning approaches [34, 37, 39–41, 44]. For instance, in the traditional ML category, [33] presented a framework for 5G that leverages Random Forest to enhance robust resource allocation efficiency. Similarly, [31] proposed a method for predicting node mobility in mobile ad hoc networks using Extreme Learning Machines (ELMs) [42].

Additionally, Markov chains have long been utilized to model a wide range of natural and artificial processes due to their versatility. In the context of mobility prediction, an early privacy-focused application was introduced by Gambs [29], which was later expanded by Gambs and Killjian for "next place" prediction [30]. Hidden Markov Models (HMMs) extend traditional Markov Models by addressing hidden events, where state transitions cannot be directly observed but are inferred from observable outputs dependent on the current state. The effectiveness of HMMs for human mobility prediction was demonstrated in [43], achieving notable accuracy. Since then, numerous studies such as [32], [35], and [36] have explored various HMM-based approaches to tackle the mobility prediction problem.

Apart from them, deep learning-based approaches include [44], which employed Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) for traffic prediction in vehicular ad hoc networks (VANETs), and [34], which introduced a cost-effective deep learning model for mobility prediction in 5G based on user location and velocity data. The Spatio-Temporal Dependency Network (STD-Net) and the Dynamic Hybrid Spatio-Temporal Network (DHSTNet), proposed in [37] and [38] respectively, were designed to model urban traffic crowd flow. Both architectures integrate CNNs and LSTMs to capture sequential temporal dependencies in traffic data.

Further advancing this domain, [39] combined LSTM for improved UE mobility prediction accuracy with a reinforcement learning algorithm to optimize network

structure selection. A lightweight single-layer artificial neural network for user location prediction is used in , while [40] proposed an LSTM-based model that incorporates historical mobility features such as location, speed, and direction to predict future user locations.

Table 2 gives an overview of the important ML work on mobility prediction we discussed above. Even if a carefully crafted ML model adapted to the particular mobility situation and dataset will give the best prediction performance, it can be hard to find such a model, and in this paper, we utilize AutoML to do this task. Then the algorithm will instead select the model and corresponding hyperparameters following one of the established ML models. This approach also has some security benefits, as we show in the paper.

2.3 Adversarial Machine Learning

Relative to the stages of learning, a report from the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) [45] classifies the attack toward machine learning model into two categories: (i) Training-time attacks and (ii) Deployment-time attacks. The common term of the former is poisoning attack [46], which can be classified into two categories: data poisoning [46, 47] where an attacker injects harmful data into the training set and model poisoning [48] where the attacker tampers with the model itself, either during training or via a compromised update mechanism. The latter can also be classified into two categories: evasion attack [49–51], where the adversary modifies input data to cause the machine learning model to make incorrect predictions, and privacy attack [52, 53] where the aim is to extract sensitive information from the model or its data.

In an earlier work , we addressed evasion attacks against mobility prediction with NWDAF. In this paper, we switch focus and look at similar attacks from a data poisoning perspective instead. As our paper targets poisoning attacks, we will further discuss those in relation to mobile network analytics below.

Poisoning attacks are often categorized according to the attacker’s knowledge. We distinguish between perfect-knowledge, limited-knowledge, and zero-knowledge [54]. In the perfect-knowledge model, the attacker has full insight regarding models and parameters in the system and is able to tune the attack accordingly. This is often also referred to as a white-box attack. On the other hand, in the zero-knowledge model or black-box attack, the attacker has no such information and can only observe the outcome of attack attempts.

In this paper, we adopt the black-box attack approach investigating how different mobility injection attacks affect mobility prediction accuracy. Such attacks can easily be performed, and the attacker will not even need to know anything about the underlying learning principles or models used by the operator. Lots of research has been devoted to poisoning situations under the less realistic white-box scenario or mixed knowledge scenarios where the attacker has more direct insight into the training process and models [55, 56].

To the best of our knowledge, no other previous work has addressed the black-box NWDAF poisoning problem. In a recent paper by Saad [57], federated learning poisoning in NWDAF systems was addressed. However, this is under a very different

Fig. 1 The lifecycle of NWDAF’s model, showing the cyclic process of initial training (green), anomaly detection (red), and retraining (blue) with decision points that determine the flow between these phases.

attack model under the assumption and that the attacker has control over a subset of NWDAF nodes in a federated learning system.

3 Background and Problem Definition

In this section, we give a background to the NWDAF model training lifecycle. This is essential as the paper is based on the NWDAF standard, which recommends continuous model updates. This in turn is related to concept drift and the corresponding strategy for retraining, which we discuss next. Finally, we define the problem addressed in the paper under the NWDAF scenario.

3.1 The Lifecycle of an NWDAF Model

The NWDAF model is defined by 3GPP [7]. It is a rather broad framework allowing different mobile network analytics functions to be implemented. The standard also discusses a mechanism for identifying abnormal UEs. There is a mandatory requirement for the operator to have the means to distinguish such abnormality within a given time window and potentially exclude their data to maintain the accuracy of NWDAF analytics (3GPP 23.288 [7], section 5.1). As anomaly detection is challenging, even if such a mechanism exists, it cannot detect all malicious activities in the network.

Figure 1 illustrates the complete lifecycle of an NWDAF model following the standard [7], highlighting the cyclic nature of the process and the decision paths based on accuracy measurements. The green, red, and blue regions in the flowchart represent different phases in the lifecycle. Below, we explain the details of the different steps:

- C1 The cycle starts with an initial training phase (green region in Figure 1) to generate the first version of the trajectory model. The model selection can be

handcrafted manually or by using an automated mechanism with AutoML. In this paper, our approach follows the model selection of the prior work [58], which involves picking the best model with AutoML. Once the best model is identified, it is deployed to the live environment to provide services to other NFs in the network. The accuracy of the deployed model is periodically checked and remeasured every predefined period. A decrease in accuracy indicates either behavioral changes of legitimate UEs or the presence of adversarial UEs in the network.

- C2 In the presence of adversarial UEs in the network (detected through decreased accuracy), the 3GPP standard mandates that the operator must have the means to distinguish the legitimate and adversarial UEs to be potentially excluded from the network. This anomaly detection phase is represented by the red region in Figure 1. The decision diamond in the flowchart determines whether accuracy returns to normal after exclusion of suspected adversarial UEs.
- C3 If the accuracy is back to normal after the exclusion of adversarial UEs (C2), the NWDAF model continues its operation along the right path in the flowchart. Otherwise, following the left path, the operator assumes that there is a shift in the (legitimate) user mobility behavior. When this happens, the assumed-to-be all benign UEs form the training set and will be used in the next retraining task (blue region in Figure 1). This retraining phase generates a new model that will be deployed to the live environment. Similar to the first situation, in this phase, the model selection can be handcrafted manually, or AutoML can be used to automate the selection.

As shown in Figure 1, this process forms a continuous cycle, where the model undergoes periodic evaluation and may be updated through either the anomaly detection phase or the retraining phase, depending on the observed accuracy patterns. The strategies discussed in this paper can be directly implemented within existing NWDAF deployments using standard ML frameworks. Implementation requires integrating an AutoML component (Auto-sklearn, FLAML, AutoGluon, or else) with the NWDAF analytics pipeline, configurable time budgets for model selection, and a mechanism to preserve model architecture across retraining cycles.

3.2 Concept drift and retraining strategies

In many ML deployments, data distributions change over time—a phenomenon known as concept drift [59]. Concept drift can gradually degrade model performance by increasing the discrepancy between training and inference data distributions. Continuous model updates could mitigate performance deterioration but may be resource-intensive and sensitive to anomalous data. From resource-efficiency and security perspectives, a selective retraining approach may be preferable. Below, we discuss potential triggers for initiating model retraining.

3.2.1 Retraining triggers

One simple way to update a model for a distribution that shifts over time is to periodically retrain the model based on fixed time intervals. However a clear drawback of this approach is that if the distribution is unchanged compared to the previous model

update, retraining would be a waste of resources. A natural improvement to periodic retraining is therefore to restrict model updates to when a significant shift in the data distribution has occurred. There are numerous methods in the prior art for detecting concept drift, and even some that additionally aim to determine if the shift is harmful to the current model performance or not [60].

Mobility prediction is a special ML application in the sense that the system can check the accuracy of its prediction in close to real time by comparing the real observed movements to the predicted. For this reason it is feasible to use a drop in accuracy as an indication of concept drift that is harmful to model performance. However, in the presence of adversarial UEs the observed accuracy can drop even without an actual change in the real mobility distribution. Consequently, additional measures are desirable to distinguish a natural drift in the distribution from intentional malicious interference. From a resource perspective, retraining should only occur if the true distribution has changed - even if the retraining strategy chosen is robust against data poisoning.

3.3 Problem Definition

As we described above, in step C2 the standard mandates that the operator shall have the possibility to identify adversarial UEs and exclude them from the network. However, it is in many cases very hard/impossible for an operator to, with high precision, determine if a UE is adversarial or not. In particular, strange mobility patterns are typically not forbidden in a mobile network. Consequently, we in this paper investigate a situation where an attacker introduces adversarial mobility into the network and how that influences the network performance, and in particular, we investigate how it impacts the NWDAF mobility prediction. As previous research has shown that “jump” patterns can have a significant performance impact on the prediction accuracy [58], we in this paper investigate how adversarial mobility patterns affect the prediction performance when using AutoML and under different retraining strategies.

4 Different operator retraining strategies

To address the identified research problem, we investigate two natural classes and three different types of hypothetical operator strategies based on the characteristics of their retraining profile, i.e., how they use AutoML during retraining tasks. We denote the two classes, A and B, respectively, and the selection is based on a more general work about continual learning in practice [61]. But, before that, we explain the time budget in AutoML as it is the main factor for classifying the strategies.

The term *time-budget* [62] refers to the maximum amount of time that the AutoML system is allowed to search for the best machine learning model and its hyperparameters given the input dataset. Essentially, it sets a runtime limit on the AutoML process. However, searching through all possible combinations of models and their hyperparameters can be computationally expensive and time-consuming. While a more extended time budget can potentially lead to a more optimized model, it does not always guarantee significantly better performance. After a certain point, the improvements might

be marginal. Hence, choosing an appropriate time budget is crucial to balance model performance and computational efficiency.

4.1 New model and data for each retraining (Strategy A)

The first strategy, A, is about constantly updating the learning process as new data comes in. In [61], it is termed as a self-correction policy where “*the policy engine is responsible for updating models by triggering retraining or other actions*”. In our case, the trigger is a lowered accuracy after the system is assumed to have separated the adversarial data points from the dataset (which is actually not the case). With the model being updated for every trigger of the policy engine, AutoML is used to select the best model at all times (both during initial training and at retraining). Strategy A is formally defined as:

A The operator selects the best model and hyperparameters both during initial training (step C1 in section 3) and during the retraining period (step C3 in section 3) using AutoML.

This is a natural and straightforward strategy to choose. In this case, setting an appropriate AutoML time budget is critical. Performing a retraining task using AutoML can be time-consuming, with a significant portion of time dedicated to finding the best model given the polluted dataset. In order to minimize the impact, a lower time budget is desirable. However, a lower time budget may result in a less accurate model and a poor selection of hyperparameters. Striking a balance between these two factors is crucial to achieving a performant model while keeping uptime high.

4.2 Old model and new data for each retraining (strategy B)

The second strategy, B, is the opposite of the first one. It diverges from the continual learning ideal by limiting the scope of retraining. This reflects a practical compromise, as highlighted in [61], between the ideal of continuous model evolution and the realities of computational and resource constraints. According to the second strategy, the operator thinks model reselection using AutoML is costly (computation, time, and cost-wise). In this case, the operator’s natural choice is to select the initial model with AutoML but retrain using the same selected model as picked initially with newer data (which, in this case, might include the adversarial data points). We formally define strategy B as follows:

B The operator selects the best model and hyperparameters with AutoML only during initial training (C1) and then retrains the same initial model and hyperparameters during the retraining period (C3) with newer data.

We further divide this retraining strategy class into two different sub-categories, depending on the allocated time budget for the initial training (C1):

B1 Short time budget.

B2 Long time budget.

For these two strategies, as the operator decided to stick with the initial model, allocating more time budget is not a problem. This is because AutoML is only used when NWDAF is not yet deployed, and spending as much time as possible in finding a suitable model can be done without affecting the live deployment in any way. Hence,

allocating a larger time budget is not as costly as in the first strategy. The main consideration is, instead, the computational cost, where a larger time budget means more resources are needed for the initial training.

It is important to note that the time budgets specified for each strategy (6 minutes for Strategy A and B1, 60 minutes for Strategy B2) inherently define their computational complexity constraints. These time budgets were selected to balance the trade-off between model quality and computational resources required, making the complexity considerations an integral part of our strategy design rather than a separate dimension of analysis. The discussion to balance these two factors is explored in section 7.4.

5 Threat Model

Several different threats exist against mobility prediction in mobile networks. Here, we are focusing on attacks against the prediction models with the goal of the attacker to degrade the prediction performance. Concerning poisoning attacks on NWDAF, as we discussed in the introduction, most previous work has considered rather advanced attack models directly on the NWDAF models or the nodes in federated learning scenarios [63].

In these attack scenarios, the attacker can directly measure the effects of an attack and adapt the position strategy based on a complete view of the training data set or direct feedback and by using optimization strategies like gradient-based poisoning [64]. When it concerns mobility prediction, this is an operator network internal function. Consequently, the prediction data is typically not available to the attacker. This is one of the reasons we do not consider poisoning attacks where the attacker has this possibility. However, one can never rule out that an attacker has direct access to UEs, which means that all kinds of UE-related attacks are relevant to study.

This is the path we have chosen to take in this paper: limit the study to UE-based mobility attacks and where the adversary only has access to these devices and no other mobility data in the network. For a mobility attack to be considered feasible, it must not require an unreasonable amount of effort. In particular, an attack that involves moving UEs (physically) throughout the network for extended durations is not practical. The resources and effort needed to carry out such an attack would outweigh any potential gains, making these types of attacks improbable and beyond the scope of this analysis.

This study operates under the assumption that an adversary possesses the capability to obtain UEs and create multiple clones with identical International Mobile Subscriber Identity (IMSI) numbers. The attack can be scaled vertically by acquiring more UEs or horizontally by increasing the number of cloned UEs. The acquisition process can be either legitimate, following standard procedures, or illegitimate if existing ones are stolen. Note that this scaling is limited as assuming the adversary can control all the UEs in the network is not feasible. It means that the adversary does not have full white-box capabilities, as it only controls a small portion of the UEs in the network. Research has demonstrated the feasibility of extracting the main secret

key from a 4G Universal Subscriber Identity Module (USIM) [65, 66]. If the adversary gains access to the primary USIM key, they may be able to duplicate it. While NWDAF and our attack are mainly intended for 5G, we envision that a similar attack can be applied in a non-standalone 5G network.

Since our primary objective is to illustrate how the presence of adversarial UEs can also impact the accuracy of legitimate UEs’ trajectory prediction **if** the operator fails to exclude the adversarial UEs before the next retraining task, we assume that the adversarial mobility from the attacker cannot be detected in step C2 in section 3, i.e., a data poisoning event has occurred. In such a worst-case scenario (given the attack that is performed), we explore what can be done to minimize the impact on the operator using the different identified strategies. In a real-world scenario, this situation could occur if a newly formed adversarial pattern is introduced by the adversary, making the system unable to detect the attack. It should be noted that the mobility model itself is not a part of the NWDAF specification, as the 3GPP standard only defines interfaces and use cases. However, we have defined a mobility model with NWDAF input and output.

6 Mobility Datasets

Real-world mobility datasets significantly enhance the quality and applicability of mobility prediction research. However, acquiring comprehensive real-world data is challenging due to privacy restrictions and practical limitations. Publicly available mobility datasets are typically derived from crowdsourced efforts or limited sets of user equipment (UEs) equipped with geolocation loggers, often lacking sufficient granularity and failing to accurately represent the mobility patterns of large populations. Luca et al. [67] summarize available datasets, highlighting that Call Detail Records (CDRs) contain sensitive information and thus are rarely publicly accessible, while GPS-based datasets, such as GeoLife, provide limited scope—only capturing 182 users over 4.5 years—or insufficient data resolution for robust analyses.

Given these constraints, researchers commonly rely on synthetic datasets generated through simulation. Synthetic datasets offer controlled environments to analyze mobility behaviors, allowing researchers to overcome limitations related to data availability and privacy concerns. In this research, we utilize two synthetic datasets: one proprietary dataset derived from Ericsson’s simulator, representing realistic network topologies and mobility patterns, and one open-source dataset generated using the ONE Simulator [68]. While the proprietary dataset provides structured scenarios closely aligned with actual network deployments, its closed nature restricts reproducibility. Conversely, our open-source dataset addresses these limitations by promoting transparency, reproducibility, and independent validation across diverse mobility scenarios.

6.1 Legitimate Mobility

Generalizing mobility for prediction is complex due to varying individual and group movement patterns [69]. We focus on the *working professional* mobility model [70], characterized by periodic home-to-office commutes, representing predictable mobility

across large populations. Both datasets reflect this structured mobility pattern, with Ericsson’s simulator based on Airtel’s real-world network deployment in India and the ONE Simulator configured to replicate comparable mobility conditions (see Table 4).

6.2 Adversarial Mobility

In a network, coarse positional data is obtained by the base station used by the UE to connect. This is therefore difficult for an adversary to alter and with the threat model in this paper the assumption is that any adversarial mobility data comes from deliberate changes to mobility patterns of actual UEs connected to the network. For this type of adversarial data, the performance of a mobility model can be affected in two ways. Firstly, since it is possible for the system to calculate the accuracy of the predictions, mobility data with a deliberately crafted difference in distribution can decrease the accuracy measured by the system. This, will not affect the accuracy of the predictions for legitimate UEs but may cause the system to trigger retraining. Secondly, if adversarial mobility data is collected and used for retraining, it is a case of data poisoning and may degrade the accuracy of the retrained model.

A previous study [58] has shown one attack, called the tuple-jumping mobility attack, as the most effective in decreasing the NWDAF Model’s accuracy. We use this type of attack in our measurement. We assume that the adversary aims to disrupt mobility prediction accuracy with minimal resources by manipulating UE mobility traces. Specifically, the attacker duplicates IMSIs and strategically positions cloned UEs at separate locations, enabling remote activation and deactivation without physical relocation. This approach effectively creates artificial, rapid positional changes (tuple-jumping), which can mislead the network operator and trigger unnecessary retraining due to perceived inaccuracies.

In Ericsson’s simulator, this attack leverages realistic network conditions, whereas in the ONE Simulator, adversarial behavior is implemented through a custom `InstantJumpMovement` model that instantaneously switches UE positions.

6.3 ONE Simulator Adaptions

The ONE Simulator [68] is widely used for modeling Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs) and opportunistic networks. Its flexible mobility model framework makes it well-suited for mobility dataset extraction.

To generate an effective open-source dataset, we adapted the ONE Simulator by:

- Implementing discrete-time simulation, JSON-based mobility logging for efficient storage and easy parsing.
- Dividing the simulation area into discrete geo-spatial sectors, facilitating structured feature extraction.
- Developing specialized movement models, including the `InstantJumpMovement`, to accurately represent adversarial behaviors.

These enhancements provide a robust basis for mobility prediction analyses, enabling independent validation through public availability [12]¹.

¹<https://github.com/nwdaf-research/dataset-attack>

6.3.1 Implementation Details

The implementation of custom mobility models and sector-based mobility tracking in the ONE Simulator required modifications to existing classes, the development of new movement models, and enhancements in mobility data reporting. This section details the software design choices, class structures, and interactions between modules.

1. Data reporting:

The `SectorMobilityReport` class captures user equipment (UE) movements by dividing the simulation world into coverage areas that correspond to gNB/eNB locations. This class extends the reporting framework in the ONE simulation environment, allowing real-time logging of sector transitions and post-simulation data restructuring.

The reporting system retrieves its configuration from the `Settings` class, enabling adjustable parameters such as logging intervals, sector size, and world dimensions. The system dynamically computes sector centers based on world size and sector resolution, ensuring spatial accuracy in tracking movements. Each UE's sector is determined using the formula:

$$\text{Sector ID} = \left(\frac{x}{\text{sectorSize}} \right) + \left(\frac{y}{\text{sectorSize}} \right) \times \text{numSectorsPerRow} \quad (1)$$

where x and y denote the UE's current coordinates, and `numSectorsPerRow` is given by:

$$\text{numSectorsPerRow} = \frac{\text{worldWidth}}{\text{sectorSize}} \quad (2)$$

The class maintains an internal state to track UE sector assignments, avoiding redundant logging when a UE remains in the same sector. When a UE transitions between sectors, the event is logged with a timestamp rounded to the nearest simulation step. The final dataset is structured into two primary sections: `movements`, which records UE transitions over time, and `sectors`, which defines the spatial boundaries of each sector.

2. Adversarial Mobility Modeling:

To introduce adversarial mobility behaviors, we implemented a specialized movement model: `InstantJumpMovement`.

The `InstantJumpMovement` model simulates adversarial mobility by assigning each UE only two fixed locations: an initial position and a destination. These locations are uniquely assigned per UE to avoid overlapping trajectories, with instantaneous position switching controlled by the parameters `stayDuration` and `teleportDelay`. The model's configuration dynamically retrieves simulation world dimensions from the `Settings` class. UE movement decisions are evaluated at each simulation step, enabling precise control of adversarial behavior timing.

The model share a modular and configurable architecture, enabling comprehensive and extensible evaluation of adversarial mobility scenarios.

3. Working-Day Movement:

The Working Day Movement Model [68] reflect structured, daily human mobility patterns. This model is designed to capture daily commuting behavior.

Our simulation follows the structure of the original model presented in [68], with adaptations tailored to the specific requirements of our study. The simulation environment was defined within a 5000×5000 meters world, encompassing 10,000 UEs engaged in structured working-day movement. The simulation was executed over six days, where the first day served as a warm-up period to stabilize mobility patterns. To introduce statistical variability, the experiment was repeated across ten independent runs, each utilizing a different random seed to ensure diverse mobility scenarios. Detailed scenario parameters are presented in Table 3

To maintain consistency with a proprietary reference dataset from Ericsson, we opted for free-space movement rather than map-based mobility. This choice ensures direct comparability between the preparatory simulation measurements without the influence of scenario-based configurations due to map layouts.

Table 3 Configured Parameters for Working Day Movement

Parameter	Value	Purpose
Movement Model	Working-Day Movement	Structured mobility model based on daily work-home routines
Simulation Time	540000s (6 days)	Ensures five full simulation days, with the first day used for warm-up
World Size	5000×5000 meters	Large-scale urban simulation setting
Speed	4.0 m/s (fixed)	Fixed movement speed to control variability in sector handovers
Own Car Probability	1.0 (100% car movement)	Exclusive use of car-based transport, eliminating pedestrian dynamics
Bus Transport	Disabled	Avoids route-based constraints to align with free-space mobility
Number of Offices	8	Distributed office locations per simulation run for 1000 UEs
Work Location	Random per run	Ensures variability across simulation iterations
Home Location	Random per UE	Assigned uniquely to each UE to prevent movement synchronization
Work Day Length	28800s (8 hours)	Fixed work duration, eliminating time variations in arrival and departure
Office Size	50 meters	Limits intra-office movements, minimizing sector switching
Group Movement	Enabled (2-10 UEs per group)	Models ride-sharing behavior by allowing shared commuting paths
Evening Activity	Disabled	Restricts movement to work-home transitions only

6.3.2 Dataset Limitations & Comparison Between Datasets

Table 4 presents a comparative analysis of important simulation parameters to highlight the key differences between the datasets.

Our mobility dataset inherits certain limitations from the Working Day Movement Model [68], including abstracting movements onto a two-dimensional plane and assuming rigid, predictable daily routines. This neglects vertical constraints, mid-day activities, and spontaneous deviations inherent in realistic mobility. Additionally, the assumption of continuous UE connectivity without considering handovers or signal degradation oversimplifies real-world network behaviors, potentially impacting communication accuracy.

Table 4 Comparison of key parameters between Ericsson’s proprietary dataset and the ONE Simulator dataset.

Aspect	Ericsson Proprietary Dataset	ONE Simulator Dataset
Simulation area size (meters)	600 x 600	5000 x 5000
Number of eNodeBs	40	168
eNodeB deployment layout	Based on Airtel India installation	Grid-based distribution
Working Professional Mobility Pattern	Quadrilateral movement	Linear (straight-line) movement

While Ericsson’s simulator proprietary dataset was structured around network-level parameters, the open-source dataset generated using the ONE Simulator offers several advantages:

- **Greater flexibility in defining mobility behaviors:** The open-source dataset allows for a wider range of mobility scenarios, making it adaptable to different research needs.
- **Higher granularity with scenario configurability :** The simulator allows for configurable mobility scenarios that enhance adaptability across different research needs. This allows researchers to fine-tune mobility models for specific conditions, improving the detection of anomalous behaviors and optimizing predictive accuracy.
- **Improved transparency and reproducibility:** Open-source datasets ensure that research findings can be independently validated, fostering collaboration and innovation in mobility prediction studies.

Despite these advantages, the proprietary dataset remains valuable due to its real-world basis, as it is derived from an actual network operator’s deployment. The combination of both datasets provides a comprehensive evaluation framework, enabling comparisons under diverse mobility conditions. In our evaluations (detailed in Section 8), we analyze the impact of both datasets on mobility prediction accuracy, particularly under adversarial conditions.

7 Simulation and Result

7.1 Simulation Environment

The UE mobility simulation and AutoML evaluation were conducted using the summarized resources in Table 5. This configuration ensured consistent results across varying adversarial proportions and model retraining strategies.

Table 5 Simulation Environment and Resource Configuration

Aspect	Details
Compute Resources	AMD EPYC 7413 (48 cores), 256 GB RAM
AutoML Frameworks	FLAML, AutoSklearn, AutoGluon
Number of Legitimate UEs	10,000
Adversarial UE Range	50–1000 (step: 50)
Simulation Duration	5 days
Training Period	Days 1–4
Testing Period	Day 5

7.2 Simulation Methodology

To provide a clear overview of the simulation methodology, Figure 2 illustrates the main steps involved in conducting our experiments, including data generation, pre-processing, AutoML strategy selection, retraining under adversarial conditions, and subsequent performance evaluation.

The simulation process begins with the initialization of the network scenario and mobility settings. Mobility data is generated for both legitimate and adversarial scenarios using the predefined models described in Section 6. The generated data then undergoes preprocessing, as detailed in Section 7.3, to prepare it for use with AutoML frameworks. In the initial phase, AutoML selects an optimal model architecture using various time budgets (ranging from 0 to 10 minutes), allowing us to analyze the impact of budget duration. Poisoning attack data is subsequently injected into the training set. Two retraining strategies are then explored: (A) repeatedly running AutoML to select a new model at each cycle, and (B) retraining the initial AutoML-selected model using either a short or long time budget. These strategies are evaluated under varying proportions of adversarial data, with model performance assessed in Section 7.7.

Fig. 2 Flowchart illustrating the simulation methodology and workflow.

7.3 Data Preprocessing

The dataset from Ericsson’s simulator (Section 6) contains three primary features: IMSI, eNodeB_path, signal_strength, where the signal strength merely indicates the UE’s connected eNodeB and is not used directly for mobility predictions. Table 6 exemplifies historical connection data for a UE IMSI 08126630, which is historically connected to eNodeB 2 and 17 at timestamp 99 and 244, respectively, where the signal strength of each connection is 0.154 and 0.199.

Table 6 Raw data

IMSI	eNodeB_path	signal_strength
08126630	'99':2,'244':17,...	'99':0.154,'244':0.199,...

We transform the data from IMSI-based to event-based to predict the future location for each UE at specific timestamps. Thus, each timestamp records multiple IMSIs connected to respective eNodeBs, with each IMSI connecting only to one eNodeB at a time. The duration a UE remains connected before switching is termed a timeslot, as defined in Equation 3.

For better predictive modeling, we enrich each event with additional contextual features:

- **enode_1-enode_4**: The history of 4 previous connected eNodeBs.
- **time_1-time_4**: The timeslot of each connection.
- **sig_st**: Signal strength of that particular connection to the target eNodeB.
- **imsi**: The IMSI of the connected UE of the target eNodeB.
- **neigh_1-neigh_4**: Top four neighboring eNodeBs of the currently connected eNodeB.
- **early_morning, morning, noon, evening, and night**: Categorizing each timestamp into five different bins.
- **home_enb**: A home eNodeB where a particular IMSI stays connected the longest.

Both Ericsson’s and the ONE Simulator datasets undergo identical preprocessing steps, with the exception that *sig_st* is unset in the ONE Simulator dataset, as it assigns eNodeBs based purely on UE geolocation within sectors.

The final enriched input variables are represented as {**enode_1, enode_2, enode_3, enode_4, time_1, time_2, time_3, time_4, sig_st, imsi, home_enb, early_morn, morning, noon, evening, night, neigh_1, neigh_2, neigh_3, neigh_4**}. The processed data is then used to model and predict the binned timeslot duration a UE maintains at a particular eNodeB. Note that the timeslot is binned to reduce the effect of small differences in continuous values, which are of less importance. Also, as the timeslot is the time spent on each eNodeB before moving to another location, classifying binned values is simpler than classifying the continuous values of many different UEs.

Fig. 3 Time budget to the accuracy for the ONE simulator data. The shaded areas represent one standard deviation across five independent runs.

7.4 Finding the optimum time budget

To determine the optimal time budget, we examine the impact of different time budgets on prediction accuracy when the training set consists exclusively of legitimate UEs. We vary the time budget from 1 to 10 minutes and observe the changes in accuracy across the three AutoML frameworks: Auto-sklearn, FLAML, and AutoGluon. Our objective is to identify the smallest time budget at which the accuracy values converge among the frameworks, as a shorter time budget is desirable to minimize the duration of the retraining process in C3.

Figure 3 depicts this relationship using the dataset generated from the ONE Simulator. The graph shows a marked increase in accuracy during the initial time budgets, with a convergence observed around the 5-minute mark for all three frameworks. Beyond this point, the accuracy values remain relatively stable, with only minor fluctuations.

Figure 4, which is based on the proprietary Ericsson dataset, exhibits a similar convergence pattern but at a slightly later point around the 6-minute mark. The accuracy values in Figure 4 also show more variability beyond the convergence point compared to Figure 3.

Fig. 4 Time budget to the accuracy for the Ericsson dataset. The shaded areas represent one standard deviation across five independent runs.

Based on these observations, we standardize the minimum time budget to 6 minutes for both datasets to maintain consistency and comparability between the current study using the ONE Simulator dataset and the previous study using the Ericsson dataset. This standardized time budget is denoted as TA for strategy A and TB1 for strategy B1.

For strategy B2, which involves a longer time budget for initial model selection, we set the time budget to be 10 times the minimum time, resulting in a budget of 60 minutes (denoted as TB2). This longer time budget is only used during the initial training phase (C1) and does not affect the live deployment of the NWDAF.

These standardized time budgets (TA, TB1, and TB2) provide a consistent baseline for evaluating the performance of the different retraining strategies (A, B1, and B2) and their effectiveness in preserving the NWDAF’s model prediction accuracy when faced with adversarial attacks.

A detailed description of the AutoML frameworks, including their configuration parameters, search spaces, and computational constraints, is provided in Appendix A.

7.5 Evaluation Metric: Mobility Prediction Accuracy

Mobility prediction in UE involves two crucial metrics: (1) location prediction at a specific time denoted as \hat{l} , and (2) timeslot prediction (\hat{s}) given that \hat{l} is accurate. The latter metric indicates how long a UE remains connected to a specific eNodeB

Table 7 Mathematical Notations and Definitions used in Simulation and Results

Notation	Definition
\hat{l}	Predicted location (eNodeB) of a UE at a specific time
\hat{s}	Predicted timeslot duration of a UE at a specific location (eNodeB)
t_1, t_2	Start and end times of the prediction period (5 days)
T	Total prediction period, where $t_2 - t_1 \in T$ (5 days)
n	Total number of mobility events in the prediction period
e	A single mobility event
$\hat{s}_{correct}$	Correctly predicted timeslot duration
$\hat{l}_{correct}$	Correctly predicted location (eNodeB)

at a particular time. For a given period of $t_2 - t_1 \in T$ with n mobility events e , the mobility prediction accuracy is calculated as the sum of correct timeslot predictions \hat{s} (when \hat{l} is correct) divided by the total number of predictions. The accuracy metric, defined in Equation 3, serves as the primary evaluation criterion used throughout our experiments to compare model performance under different adversarial conditions and retraining strategies.

$$\mathbf{Accuracy} = \frac{\sum_{e=0}^n (\hat{s}_{correct} | \hat{l}_{correct})}{n} \quad (3)$$

Table 7 summarizes all the notations used in this paper.

7.6 Attack on the training set

Given the pre-processed data and the minimum time budget mentioned earlier, we investigate the impact of adversarial attacks on hypothetical operators following strategies A, B1, and B2. Since the operator is assumed to be unable to distinguish adversarial UEs from legitimate ones, the retraining process incorporates both adversarial and legitimate data, simulating real-world data poisoning scenarios. We analyze how this poisoned retraining affects the model’s performance when tested on *legitimate* UEs. This means that while we consider attack during re-training, we test the accuracy under *normal* conditions. This allows us to verify the poisoning effect on the mobility prediction accuracy under normal conditions.

The poisoning attack is carried out by gradually increasing the proportion of adversarial UEs in the training set, ranging from 50 to 1000 adversarial UEs out of 10,000 legitimate UEs. This corresponds to an adversarial proportion of 0.005 to 0.1 relative to the total number of legitimate UEs. The interval of 50 adversarial UEs is chosen to provide a fine-grained analysis of how the NWDAF’s performance degrades as the number of adversarial UEs increases. For each proportion of adversarial UEs and each strategy, we retrain the model using the AutoML process five times. Each retraining cycle uses a mix of legitimate and adversarial data, and the model is then evaluated exclusively on legitimate UEs to assess the impact of adversarial poisoning. For strategy A, each retraining cycle produces a different model with different hyperparameters since AutoML is involved. For strategies B1 and B2, the same model architecture selected during the initial AutoML phase is used, with the initial AutoML-based model selection performed using a time budget of 6 minutes for strategy B1 and 60 minutes for strategy B2. After retraining, we compute the mean and standard deviation

Fig. 5 FLAML with the Ericsson dataset. Strategy B2 consistently outperforms other strategies with higher and more stable accuracy across all adversarial proportions. The shaded areas represent one standard deviation across five independent runs.

of accuracy across the five retraining runs for each adversarial proportion and each strategy.

7.7 Results

In this section, we present the experimental results comparing our three retraining strategies under varying proportions of adversarial UEs. We evaluate three different AutoML frameworks (FLAML, AutoSklearn, and AutoGluon) to ensure a representative coverage of diverse model search strategies.

7.7.1 FLAML

Figures 5 and Figure 6 show the percentage accuracy versus the proportion of adversarial UEs to legitimate UEs for the Ericsson Dataset and the ONE simulator Dataset, respectively. In the Ericsson Dataset (Figure 5), B2-FLAML (long time budget at initial training, then re-using the same model) consistently achieves the highest or near-highest accuracy values (typically around 70%–75%) despite adversarial UEs activity. The fully updated approach A-FLAML (green) shows larger fluctuations, sometimes dropping to about 55% but occasionally going as high as 75%. Meanwhile, B1-FLAML (red) remains relatively steady, hovering around 60%–65%.

For the ONE simulator Dataset (Figure 6), B1-FLAML surprisingly outperforms B2-FLAML by a small margin across most adversarial proportions. This suggests that the more extensive time budget in B2-FLAML may have led to a degree of overfitting for

Fig. 6 FLAML with the ONE simulator dataset. Strategy B1 consistently outperforms other strategies with higher accuracy across all adversarial proportions. The shaded areas represent one standard deviation across five independent runs.

this particular dataset, slightly reducing its robustness to adversarial inputs. Regardless, both B1 and B2 remain more stable than A-FLAML, whose fully reselected model at each retraining still exhibits higher variance. Overall, the general trend persists that retraining a robust initial model yields better resilience to data poisoning, and reselecting the model yields worse results with a downward trend and high variations.

7.7.2 AutoSklearn

The results with `AutoSklearn` are presented in Figure 7 and Figure 8. A key observation here is that `B2-AutoSklearn` (long initial AutoML search) achieves the highest and most stable accuracy for both Ericsson Dataset and ONE simulator Dataset, reaching up to 80%–85% in the Ericsson Dataset. `B1-AutoSklearn`, in contrast, hovers around 60%–65% in the Ericsson Dataset and around 50%–55% in the ONE simulator Dataset. The fully updated approach `A-AutoSklearn` (green) is quite sensitive to adversarial data: its accuracy significantly degrades as the proportion of adversaries increases, dropping below 30% for higher adversarial shares in the Ericsson Dataset. Similar trends, albeit at slightly different levels, are visible in the ONE simulator Dataset results. This reinforces our general finding: *reselecting a new model at each retraining can be counterproductive in adversarial environments*, whereas a robust model discovered during the initial search (in an optimum way; does not have to be longer as shown in the previous FLAML figures) remains more resilient. Similar

Fig. 7 AutoSklearn with the Ericsson dataset. Strategy B2 consistently outperforms other strategies with higher and more stable accuracy across all adversarial proportions. The shaded areas represent one standard deviation across five independent runs.

to FLAML, in AutoSklearn, reselecting the model yields (way) worse results with a downward trend and high variations.

7.7.3 AutoGluon

Figure 9 and Figure 10 depict the results for **AutoGluon**. In the Ericsson Dataset (Figure 9), the strategy **B2-AutoGluon** (long time budget at initial training) typically achieves the highest accuracy, around 70%–75%, while both **B1-AutoGluon** (red) and **A-AutoGluon** (green) cluster around 40%–50% with some variation.

However, in the ONE simulator Dataset (Figure 10), **B1-AutoGluon** consistently outperforms **B2-AutoGluon** by a modest but noticeable margin. Similar to our observations with FLAML, the longer AutoML search in **B2-AutoGluon** may be causing overfitting in this particular scenario, slightly reducing its robustness to adversarial data. Consequently, **B1-AutoGluon** emerges as the best performer for the ONE simulator Dataset, maintaining higher stability and accuracy compared to both **B2-AutoGluon** and the fully updated **A-AutoGluon**, whose accuracy fluctuates more.

Overall, across both datasets, **B2-AutoGluon** or **B1-AutoGluon** stands out as more robust than **A-AutoGluon**. As with the other frameworks, re-running AutoML at every retraining (strategy A) exposes the model to considerable variance and reduced accuracy under higher adversarial proportions. Compared to FLAML and AutoSklearn, AutoGluon does not show a similar trend for A as the performance is relatively stable;

Fig. 8 AutoSklearn with the ONE simulator dataset. Strategy B2 consistently outperforms other strategies with higher accuracy across all adversarial proportions. The shaded areas represent one standard deviation across five independent runs.

however, the trend on A compared to B1 and B2 is still the same: it has the worst result compared to the rest.

7.7.4 Summary of Findings

Our results reveal that *re-running AutoML at every retraining* (A) tends to exhibit higher variance and greater vulnerability to adversarial data across both datasets. In general, *retraining a model selected during the initial AutoML phase* (B1 or B2) is more robust. However, the best choice between B1 and B2 can depend on the dataset and AutoML framework:

- **Ericsson dataset:** Strategy B2 (longer AutoML budget initially) frequently achieves the highest accuracy and displays stronger resilience to adversarial proportions up to 10%. Strategy B1 is typically in between B2 and A in performance.
- **The ONE simulator dataset:** In some cases (particularly FLAML and AutoGluon), B1 slightly outperforms B2, likely due to the latter’s susceptibility to overfitting when the search space is extensively explored. This indicates that a long initial search does not guarantee the most robust model in every scenario.

Overall, we see that *spending an appropriate (rather than maximal) time on the initial AutoML search* can yield models that remain more resistant to data poisoning

Fig. 9 AutoGluon with the Ericsson dataset. Strategy B2 consistently outperforms other strategies with higher and more stable accuracy across all adversarial proportions. The shaded areas represent one standard deviation across five independent runs.

during subsequent retraining. While B2 often retains the highest accuracy in adversarial settings for the old dataset, a more moderate search (B1) can be equally or more effective in the new dataset. In all cases, strategies B1 and B2 consistently surpass A in mitigating the impact of adversarial data.

All presented results represent averages over five independent simulation runs, with standard deviations visualized as shaded regions around each line in the figures. Notably, Strategy B (initial model retraining) consistently exhibits low variance, reflecting genuine stability across runs, whereas Strategy A displays larger variance, highlighting its inherent inconsistency under adversarial retraining conditions.

7.7.5 Deployment Considerations for NWDAF Operators

The retraining strategies evaluated in this study can be directly integrated into NWDAF-based network operations with minimal architectural changes. Based on our findings, we list the practical findings for mobile network operators:

- **Operator Accessibility and Maintainability:** AutoML simplifies model selection and tuning, allowing operators without specialized ML expertise to deploy and maintain predictive models. This reduces operational overhead and lowers the barrier to entry for advanced mobility analytics.
- **Model Selection Integration:** AutoML framework can be embedded into the NWDAF analytics pipeline to support a range of time budgets for model selection.

Fig. 10 AutoGluon with the ONE simulator dataset. Strategy B1 consistently outperforms other strategies with higher and more stable accuracy across all adversarial proportions. The shaded areas represent one standard deviation across five independent runs.

- **Model Retention:** Operators should persist with the initially selected model architecture after training, and use it for subsequent retraining cycles. This reduces the risk of performance degradation due to adversarial poisoning.
- **Retraining Triggering:** Retraining triggers are implemented based on real-time accuracy drops in prediction, as discussed in Section 3.2.1. However, additional measures are desirable to distinguish a natural drift in the distribution from intentional malicious interference.
- **Adaptability to Resource Budgets:** Our evaluation shows that AutoML-based strategies can maintain competitive performance even with shorter time budgets (e.g., 6 minutes). This flexibility supports deployment across a broad spectrum of infrastructure capacities and budget levels.

8 Threats to Validity

While our study provides insights into the impact of adversarial UEs on AutoML-based mobility prediction, certain limitations in our experimental setup and parameter choices should be acknowledged. Below, we discuss key potential threats to validity.

8.1 Modified Hyperparameters for AutoGluon in Strategy B2

For the B2 retraining strategy using AutoGluon, the original CatBoost model parameters for both timeslot and eNodeB prediction were set as follows:

```
original_parameters = {
    'iterations': 10000,
    'learning_rate': 0.05,
    'random_seed': 0,
    'allow_writing_files': False,
    'eval_metric': 'Accuracy'
}
```

However, due to the excessive computational cost associated with retraining (each training run taking approximately 9 hours and needing to be repeated for each adversarial proportion increment from 50 to 1000 in steps of 50), we made the following modifications to reduce runtime while maintaining model performance:

```
new_parameters = {
    'iterations': 1000,           # Reduced from 10,000
    'learning_rate': 0.1,       # Increased from 0.05
    'random_seed': 0,
    'allow_writing_files': False,
    'eval_metric': 'Accuracy',
    'early_stopping_rounds': 100 # Added early stopping
}
```

These adjustments aimed to balance efficiency and accuracy. The reduction in iterations significantly shortened training time (to ~ 1 hour), while the increase in learning rate and early stopping ensured that the model still converged effectively without excessive loss in performance. While we observed minimal differences in accuracy between the modified and original settings, it is possible that these changes influenced our final results.

8.2 Disabled Ensemble Models in AutoGluon and AutoSklearn for Strategies B1 and B2

For strategies B1 and B2, we disabled ensemble-based models in both AutoGluon and AutoSklearn. The primary reason for this decision was the impracticality of retraining multiple models separately, which would have significantly increased computational overhead. Ensemble learning typically involves training multiple base models and combining their predictions, leading to increased training time and memory usage. Since our study involved multiple retraining cycles under different adversarial settings, maintaining ensemble-based models would have made the evaluation process infeasible within a reasonable timeframe. Consequently, the selected model for both strategies B1 and B2 is always a single model without any stacking or ensembling techniques. It is important to note that FLAML does not inherently use traditional ensemble techniques such as stacking or bagging, unlike AutoGluon and AutoSklearn. Instead, FLAML focuses on efficient model selection through cost-frugal optimization. As a

result, ensemble disabling was only relevant for AutoGluon and AutoSklearn in our study, while FLAML remained unaffected by this consideration.

9 Conclusion

In this paper, we explored how adversarial data poisoning from adversarial UE mobility patterns can undermine the accuracy of NWDAF-based mobility and consequently affect the network service of non-malicious nodes in the network. We have particular studies when operators rely on AutoML for model selection and retraining. We proposed and evaluated three different retraining strategies—(A) re-running AutoML at every retraining, (B1) performing a single short-budget AutoML search initially, and (B2) using a more extensive AutoML search initially—across two distinct mobility datasets (Ericsson’s proprietary dataset and a new ONE simulator dataset) and three AutoML frameworks (FLAML, AutoSklearn, and AutoGluon).

Our results consistently show that re-selecting the model at every retraining (A) is highly sensitive to adversarial UEs and produces greater variance in accuracy. By contrast, retraining a single, initially optimized model (B1 or B2) yields more stable performance under poisoning attacks. Interestingly, we find that while B2 (a longer initial AutoML search) often outperforms B1 in one dataset, it may be more prone to overfitting in another, causing B1 to sometimes yield better resilience, i.e., the choice, can be influenced by the dataset characteristics and AutoML framework.

While Strategy B2 requires a longer initial AutoML search (60 minutes vs. 6 minutes for Strategy B1), its computational cost is negligible in practical deployments. Optimal time budgets may differ depending on the operator’s subscriber count, network complexity, and mobility patterns. Larger operators might benefit from longer searches, whereas smaller operators could achieve robustness with shorter searches. At current cloud computing prices (2025)², our experimental setup (48 cores, 256GB RAM) costs approximately \$3–6 per hour. This minor, scalable investment is insignificant relative to the total 5G infrastructure and NWDAF deployment costs, making strategy B2 feasible even for resource-limited operators. Furthermore, enhanced robustness against adversarial attacks can result in substantial long-term savings through optimized network resource use and improved resilience against threats to mobility prediction.

This paper focused on attacks from mobile users without direct access to network functions or prediction outputs. Future work could explore stronger adversaries with access to prediction results, potentially allowing more sophisticated and optimized attacks. Although such attacks are much less feasible and might not be justified considering the gain given to an attacker, it would be an interesting continuation of this work to investigate threat models with more power given to the attacker.

Although our heuristic-based time budgets illustrate how a more thorough initial model selection can increase robustness, finding the *optimal* (or near-optimal) training budget for each combination of dataset and AutoML framework remains an open question. Automating this process, i.e., through adaptive or meta-level optimization,

²<https://aws.amazon.com/ec2/pricing/on-demand/>

could systematically identify the best trade-off between search time and generalization (especially under adversarial conditions), thereby further reducing the risks of overfitting or underfitting that arise from fixed schedules. Exploring such a systematic approach to time-budget tuning is a natural next step for future research. Additionally, integrating advanced anomaly detection methods with the proposed retraining strategies could further enhance NWDAF resilience by effectively filtering adversarial data. Finally, employing model explainability techniques to understand which model characteristics contribute to adversarial robustness could enable operators to select models more efficiently.

10 Compliance with Ethical Standards

The mobility data provided in the study are from the two simulated frameworks only and do not include any personal information or data from real human interactions.

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A AutoML Implementation Details

To ensure reproducibility of our experiments, this appendix provides detailed information about the three AutoML frameworks used in our study, including their specific configurations, search spaces, and computational constraints.

A.1 AutoML Frameworks and Versions

We employed three state-of-the-art AutoML frameworks that represent different approaches to automated model selection: **Auto-sklearn (version 0.14.6)**, **FLAML (version 1.2.2)**, **AutoGluon (version 0.6.0)**.

A.2 Search Spaces and Optimization Strategies

Each framework employs different search spaces and optimization strategies:

A.2.1 Auto-sklearn

We configured Auto-sklearn with the following parameters:

```
model = autosklearn_clf.AutoSklearnClassifier(  
    n_jobs=-1, # Use all available  
        CPU cores  
    memory_limit=None, # No memory  
        constraints  
    time_left_for_this_task=time_budget, # Time budget in  
        seconds
```

```

ensemble_size=1, # For Strategy B,
  disable_ensembling
delete_tmp_folder_after_terminate=True # Clean up
  temporary files
)

```

For Strategy A, ensemble learning was enabled with the default ensemble size, while for Strategies B1 and B2, we disabled ensembling by setting `ensemble_size=1` to ensure we could extract a single reusable model.

A.2.2 FLAML

FLAML was configured as follows:

```

model = AutoML()
model.fit(X_train, y_train,
  task="classification",
  time_budget=time_budget, # Time budget in seconds
  metric='mae', # Optimization metric
  seed=42, # For reproducibility
  estimator_list=estimator_list # Algorithms to consider
)

```

FLAML’s cost-frugal approach adaptively allocates more time to promising model configurations, making it particularly efficient for the time-constrained scenarios in our study.

A.2.3 AutoGluon

AutoGluon was configured as follows:

```

model = TabularPredictor(label=target_column).fit(
  train_data=train_data,
  time_limit=time_budget, # Time budget in seconds
  presets=['optimize_for_deployment'] # Optimization preset
)

```

For Strategy B, we disabled ensemble models by setting:

```

excluded_model_types=['WEIGHTED', 'ENS_WEIGHTED', '\\
SIMPLE_ENS_WEIGHTED', 'STACKER']
fit_weighted_ensemble=False
num_stack_levels=0
num_bag_folds=0

```

A.3 Computational Constraints and Time Budgets

All experiments were conducted on a server with 48 cores of an AMD EPYC 7413 processor and 256 GB of memory. For each framework, we standardized the time budgets as follows:

- **Strategy A:** 6 minutes (360 seconds) per training run
- **Strategy B1:** 6 minutes (360 seconds) for initial model selection
- **Strategy B2:** 60 minutes (3600 seconds) for initial model selection

These time budgets were determined through preliminary experiments (as shown in Figures 4 and 3 in the main paper) where we observed convergence in performance around the 6-minute mark. The 10x longer time budget for Strategy B2 allowed for more extensive exploration of the search space during the initial training phase.

Memory limits were not explicitly set, allowing the frameworks to utilize the available system memory as needed. However, for Auto-sklearn, we used `per_run_time_limit=60` seconds to avoid excessively complex models that might overfit.

A.4 Data Processing

For all frameworks, the input data underwent identical preprocessing steps as described in Section 7.3 of the main paper. The feature set included historical connected eNodeBs (previous 4 locations), connection timestamps, signal strength, IMSI identifier, home eNodeB, time-of-day indicators, and neighboring eNodeB information.

The mobility prediction problem was formulated as a multi-class classification task, where the models predicted both the next location (eNodeB) and the duration (timeslot) a UE would remain connected at that location.

By adhering to these standardized configurations across all three AutoML frameworks, we ensured a fair comparison while maintaining the distinct characteristics of each framework’s optimization approach. The corresponding mobility dataset has been made available in our repository to facilitate reproducibility.